

Reactivity and Mass Spectral Studies on bis-(β -diketonato)-beryllium (II) chelates*

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Bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II), bis-(*o*-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) and bis-(ω -bromo acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) were isolated in pure condition. These along with other bis-(β -diketonato)-beryllium(II) chelates exhibit chemical reactivity and were found to undergo non-destructive electrophilic substitution reactions like nitration, bromination and chlorination. The nitro- or halogeno-substituted beryllium chelates were isolated and were characterized by their elemental analyses and by their i.r. and n.m.r. spectra. The mass spectral studies revealed that upon electron impact, the beryllium chelates break-down in a well defined manner and provide examples in ion-rearrangement reactions leading to changes in metal valency.

Although the chemical reactions of metal chelates, particularly acetylacetonates have received considerable attention in recent years,¹⁻⁹ there seems to be only a few reports on the differences in reactivity of complexes with different central atoms.¹⁰ Reactions of chelated ligands containing β -dicarbonyl moiety other than acetylacetone have also received meagre attention.⁶ The attempted nitration of chromium(III) chelates of benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane with copper nitrate-acetic anhydride mixtures resulted in destruction of these chelates.⁵ Fluorosubstituted metal acetylacetonates failed to form nitro derivatives and in a similar way failed to undergo bromination.⁵ That the electron density at the central carbon atom of the chelate ring is an important factor in the success or failure of these substitutions is evident from the fact that bis-(ethylenediamine)-2,4-pentanedionocobalt(III) cation cannot be brominated even under vigorous conditions.²⁴ As a part of a general study of the reactions of coordinated ligands we have investigated the electrophilic substitution reactions of bis-(β -diketonato)beryllium(II) chelates and the results of our studies are presented here.

The potential of mass spectrometry in the structural elucidation of coordination compounds and also the importance of the effect of change in metal valency on the mode of ion dissociation have recently been demonstrated.¹¹⁻¹⁴ The behaviour of beryllium chelates and some of their bromo-substituted chelates under electron impact (70 eV) have been studied and the salient features of the mass spectra of these compounds are also presented. Bis-(β -diketonato)-beryllium chelates were chosen for our investigations because of their considerable stability and their high volatility.

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EXPERIMENTAL

The infrared spectra of the compounds in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord spectrophotometer, model 137E, equipped with sodium chloride optics. The n.m.r. spectra were measured on a Varian Associates Model A-60 spectrometer operating at 60 Mc/s with TMS as internal standard. The mass spectra were recorded on CEC 21-110B (USA) Double focussing mass spectrometer at a voltage of 70 eV and a current of 20 milliamperes.

The purity of the ligands used in this work was checked from their elemental analyses and from their m.p.s. (or b.p.). ω -Bromo acetoacetanilide was prepared according to the method described by Hasegawa.¹⁵ 2,5-Dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilide (Hoechst Dyes and Chemicals), *o*-chloroacetoacetanilide (M/s. Union Carbide and Carbon Chemicals Division, USA) and acetoacetanilide (E.Merck) were further purified by recrystallisation from alcohol. Acetoacetdiethylamide (Fluka AG., Chemische Fabrik, Buchs, SG) was distilled prior to use.

Bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II): To a solution of 2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilide (2.7 g; 0.01 mole) in alcohol (40 ml.) was added, with stirring, beryllium nitrate trihydrate (0.93 g; 0.005 mole) in alcohol (15 ml.). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5 with dilute ammonia (1 : 1). The precipitated white complex was collected on a filter, washed with water and dried. The solid was recrystallised from chloroform. Yield, 1.7 g. (62%), m.p. 235°. Found : C, 51.89; H, 4.43; Be, 1.5%. Required for $C_{24}H_{26}Cl_2N_2O_8Be$: C, 52.40; H, 4.71; Be, 1.64%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3300(w), 3220(w), 2900*(vs), 1600(s), 1550(s,b), 1480*(m), 1460(m), 1420(m), 1395⁺(s), 1330(m), 1298(m), 1275(s), 1220(s), 1200(m), 1180(m), 1170(w), 1070(m), 1050(s), 1038(w), 1005(s), 968(s), 858(m), 825(s, b), 772(m), 742(w), 730(m).

Mass spectral data (m/e) : 553, 551, 549*, 520, 518, 467, 465, 450, 394.2, 364, 363, 279, 277, 268, 264, 249, 235*, 221, 213, 198, 187, 174, 172, 85, 78, 43.

Bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium (II): A thick slurry of freshly prepared beryllium hydroxide (0.43 g; 0.01 mole) in alcohol was made and to this was added slowly, with stirring, *o*-chloroacetoacetanilide (4.2 g; 0.02 mole) in alcohol (50 ml.). The stirring was continued for 4 hrs. The white solid obtained was collected on a filter, washed with water and recrystallised from chloroform. Yield, 2.8 g. (65%). Found : C, 55.16; H, 3.69; Be, 1.90%. Required for $C_{20}H_{18}Cl_2N_2O_4Be$: C, 55.82; H, 4.20; Be, 2.10%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3300(m), 2900*(vs), 1600(s), 1550(s,b), 1480*(s), 1440(s), 1420(w), 1380*(m), 1318(s,b), 1278(w), 1240(m), 1220(w), 1198(m), 1130(w), 1050(s), 1042(s), 987(s,b), 935(w), 830(s), 800(s), 762(s,b), 742(w), 694(w).

Mass spectral data (m/e) : 433, 431, 429⁺, 394, 361.2*, 347, 345, 305, 303, 219, 210, 183, 128, 127, 92, 91, 85, 43.

* Nujol : vs = very strong; s = strong; m = medium; w = weak; b = broad.

+ molecular ion; * meta-stable peak.

Bis-(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium (II) : To a solution of ω -bromoacetoacetanilide (2.6 g; 0.01 mole) in alcohol (40 ml.) was added, with stirring, a solution of beryllium nitrate trihydrate (0.93 g; 0.005 mole) in alcohol (20 ml.). The pH of the solution was adjusted to 5.5 with dilute ammonia (1 : 1). The white solid that separated out was collected on a filter, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from alcohol. Yield, 1.49 g. (53.8%). Found : C, 45.6; H, 4.39; Be, 1.65%. Required for $C_{20}H_{18}Br_2N_2O_4Be$: C, 46.20; H, 3.47; Be, 1.74%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3590(m), 3400(m), 3290(m), 3198(w), 2900*(vs), 1600(s), 1580(s), 1548(m), 1505(m), 1478*(m), 1445(s), 1380*(m), 1340(s), 1304(w), 1278(s), 1218(m), 1185(m), 1162(w), 1118(m), 1045(w), 1038(m), 1008(w), 998(s) 908(m), 860(m), 835(m), 798(m), 765(s), 692(m).

Bis-(2-bromo-1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium (II) : *N*-Bromosuccinimide (3.56 g; 0.02 mole) in $CHCl_3$ (50 ml.) was added slowly with stirring to bis-(1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium(II)¹⁶ (4.55 g; 0.01 mole) in $CHCl_3$ (50 ml.). The stirring was continued for 4 hrs. After completion of the reaction the volume of the solution was reduced to 20 ml. and the excess of NBS was removed by preferential precipitation, with petroleum-ether (60°–80°), filtered and the solvent was evaporated. The solid obtained was purified by repeated crystallisation from benzene and petroleum-ether and briefly dried under vacuum. Yield, 1.10 g. (18%). Found : C, 59.37; H, 3.72; Be, 1.38%. Required for $C_{30}H_{20}O_4Br_2Be$: C, 58.72; H, 3.30; Be, 1.47%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 2900*(vs), 1600(m), 1530(s,b), 1445(s,b), 1345*(s,b), 1318(m), 1292(s), 1220(w), 1180(m), 1112(s), 1078(m), 1035(s), 1005(m) 985(s,b), 930(m), 868(s,b), 850(s), 772(w), 730(m), 700(s,b).

Mass spectral data (m/e) : 615, 613, 611*, 534, 466*, 455, 386.8*, 326, 312, 310, 301, 233, 232, 154, 105, 77.

Bis-(2-bromo-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium (II) : The bromination was carried out in a similar manner as described above, starting with bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II)¹⁶ (3.31 g; 0.01 mole) and NBS (3.56 g; 0.02 mole). The material was purified by recrystallisation from benzene and petroleum-ether. Yield, 1.50 g. (30.8%), m.p. 100°. Found : C, 50.57; H, 3.75; Be, 1.75%. Required for $C_{20}H_{16}O_4Br_2Be$: C, 49.10; H, 3.28; Be, 1.84%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 2900*(vs), 1610(s), 1540(s,b), 1456*(s,b), 1360*(s,b), 1322(w), 1300(w), 1290(w), 1165(m), 1150(s), 1110(w), 1080(m), 1025(s,b), 1002(w), 980(w), 940(m), 845(s,b), 720(s,b), 682(m).

Mass spectral data (m/e) : 491, 489, 487*, 474, 472, 410, 408, 342*, 266, 264, 248, 241, 239, 170, 168, 105, 103, 92, 89, 77, 63, 51, 43.

Bis-(3-bromo-2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium (II) : This compound was prepared in the same way as above from bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) (2.75 g; 0.005 mole) and NBS. Yield, 0.80 g; (22.6%), m.p. 229°. Found : C, 41.00; H, 4.31; Be, 1.16%. Required for $C_{24}H_{24}O_8N_2Cl_2Br_2Be$: C, 40.67; H, 3.41; Be, 1.27%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3298(m), 2900*(vs), 1600(s), 1535(s,b), 1460*(s,b), 1390*(s), 1330(w), 1290(m), 1265(s), 1240(s), 1214(s), 1180(s), 1170(m), 1078(s), 1028(s,b), 990(m), 975(m), 885(m), 865(s,b), 835(w), 742(s), 730(m), 715(w), 675(m).

Mass spectral data (m/e) . 711, 709, 707, 705*, 626, 595, 559*, 543, 528, 523, 521, 519, 465, 463, 443, 441, 439, 357, 351, 344, 342, 331, 213, 198, 187, 180, 172, 78

Bis-(3-bromo-o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium (II) : This compound was prepared in the same way as above from bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) (4.3 g; 0.01 mole) and NBS. Yield, 1.6 g (27.2%), m.p. 204°. Found : C, 41.07; H, 2.14; Be, 1.52%. Required for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Br}_2\text{Be}$: C, 40.84; H, 2.74; Be, 1.53%.

Bromination, with NBS in CHCl_3 or with bromine in CHCl_3 , of bis-(acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)¹⁷ bis-(acetoacetdiethylamidato)-beryllium(II)¹⁸ and bis-(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) resulted in partial bromination of the parent chelates as shown by their n.m.r. spectra.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3290(m), 2900*(vs), 1600(s), 1598(m), 1530(s), 1450*(s), 1400(w), 1378*(m), 1318(s), 1260(m), 1230(m), 1130(w), 1080(m), 1055(m), 1040(w), 1030(w), 990(m), 940(m), 880(m), 860(m), 848(s), 800(m), 748(s), 725(w).

Mass spectral data (m/e) : 591, 589, 587, 585*, 507, 505, 459, 427, 425, 423, 379, 360.2*, 345, 343, 297, 263, 261, 219, 217, 183, 127, 78, 63, 55, 43.

Bis-(2-chloro-1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium (II) : N-Chloro succinimide (1.34 g; 0.01 mole) in chloroform (40 ml.) was added slowly, with stirring, to bis-(1,3-diphenylpropane diono)-beryllium(II) (2.28 g; 0.005 mole) in chloroform (50 ml.). The other experimental details followed were similar to bromination experiments. The product was purified by repeated crystallisation from benzene and petroleum-ether and finally dried under vacuum. Yield, 0.80 g. (30.5%). Found : C, 69.01; H, 3.55; Be, 1.80%. Required for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{Be}$: C, 68.73; H, 3.8; Be, 1.72%.

Attempts to chlorinate, in a similar way, bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) and bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II), however, resulted in partial chlorination of the starting materials.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 2950*(vs), 1600(m), 1555(s), 1540(s), 1485*(s), 1460(m), 1385*(s), 1350(m), 1300(m), 1230(m), 1180(w), 1160(w), 1120(w), 1085(m), 1030(m), 1005(m), 965(m), 865(m), 840(b,m), 795(w), 755(m), 730(m), 695(m).

Bis-(2-nitro-1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium (II) : To bis-(1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium(II) (2.28 g; 0.004 mole) in freshly distilled acetic anhydride (30 ml.) cooled to 0°-5° and stirred magnetically was added a slight excess of nitric acid (A.R. grade, sp.gr. 1.42; 1.2 ml.) previously cooled to 0°-5°, dropwise. After 15 min. a yellow precipitate was obtained. The stirring was continued for 1 hr. and the temperature, during this period, was maintained at 0°-5°. The cooling bath was removed and the stirring was continued at

room temperature for 2 hrs. The contents were poured into water and the yellow product was collected on a filter, washed with water and dried. The product was recrystallised from benzene and petroleum ether. Yield, 1.2 g. (44%), m.p. 230°. Found : C, 66.85; H, 3.23; Be, 1.30%. Required for $C_{30}H_{20}O_8N_2Be$: C, 66.06; H, 3.7; Be, 1.65%.

The nitro product was also prepared¹⁹ using beryllium-nitrate trihydrate in acetic anhydride and 1,3-diphenylpropanedione. Yield, 55%, m.p. 231°. Found : C, 67.1; H, 3.50; Be, 1.30%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 2960*(vs), 1600(m), 1550(s), 1525(m), 1495(m), 1462*(s), 1385*(s), 1345(w), 1330(m), 1300(w), 1238(m), 1165(m), 1085(m), 1025(m), 962(m), 870(m), 850(b,m), 760(m), 732(m), 690(w).

Bis-(2-nitro-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium (II) : This was prepared in a similar way using well-cooled nitric acid (as the nitrating agent) and bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) (3.31 g; 0.01 mole). Yield, 3 g. (71%), m.p. 210°. Found : C, 57.54; H, 3.69; Be, 2.66%. Required for $C_{20}H_{16}O_8N_2Be$: C, 57.01; H, 3.80; Be, 2.14%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 2960*(vs), 1610(m), 1585(s), 1535(s), 1470*(s), 1440(w), 1390*(s,b), 1330(m), 1180(m), 1102(m), 1085(w), 1035(w), 1015(m), 1002(m), 945(m), 900(s), 872(w), 850(s,b), 822(w), 808(w), 748(s), 715(m), 696(m).

Bis-(3-nitro-o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium (II) : This compound was prepared in a similar way using bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) (4.3 g; 0.01 mole) and nitric acid. Yield, 1.9 g (36.5%), m.p. 160°. Found : C, 47.08; H, 3.50; Be, 1.69%. Required for $C_{20}H_{16}O_8Cl_2N_4Be$: C, 46.17; H, 3.10; Be, 1.73%.

Infrared absorption maxima (in cm^{-1}) of the compound : 3300(w), 2950*(vs), 1605(m), 1560(m), 1525(m), 1475*(s), 1382*(m), 1330(m), 1230(w), 1200(w), 1155(m), 1020(m), 990(w), (945(m) 915(w), 882(w), 850(b,m), 805(m), 775(w), 765(m), 710(w).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The principal result which is confirmed in these studies is that bis-(β -diketonato)-beryllium(II) chelates exhibit the chemical behaviour expected for reactive aromatic systems. The central hydrogen atom on the chelate rings is replaced by a nitro group or by a halogen atom under apparently electrophilic conditions. N-bromosuccinimide (or NCS) in chloroform rapidly brominated (or chlorinated) the chelates. Bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II), bis-(o-chloro acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) and bis-(ω -bromo acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) were isolated for the first time and on bromination the first two chelates gave bis-(3-bromo-2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloro acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) and bis-(3-bromo-o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II). However, bromination of the third chelate and the beryllium chelates of acetoacetanilide and acetoacetdiethylamide with NBS or bromine in chloroform resulted in partial bromination of the chelates. Bis-(1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanediono)-beryllium(II) and bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II), under similar conditions of bromination gave bis-(2-bromo-1,3-diphenyl propanediono)-beryllium(II) and bis-(2-bromo-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II),

Bis-(2-chloro-1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium(II) was isolated by employing *N*-chloro succinimide instead of NBS. However, chlorination of bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) and bis-(*o*-chloro acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) resulted in partially chlorinated products.

Bis-(2-nitro-1,3-diphenyl propanediono)-beryllium(II), bis-(2-nitro-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) and bis-(3-nitro-*o*-chloro acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) were isolated using nitric acid as the nitrating agent²⁰ and also on reacting the respective ligand with a solution of beryllium nitrate trihydrate in acetic anhydride.¹⁹

The infrared spectra of the substituted beryllium chelates are very similar, and the same pattern of changes appears in the i.r. spectra of the unsubstituted and substituted chelates. The spectra of the chelates of 2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloro-acetoacetanilide, *o*-chloro-acetoacetanilide and ω -bromoacetoacetanilide and the other unsubstituted beryllium chelates show two strong absorption bands in the region 1500–1600 cm^{-1} . The higher frequency band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the beryllium chelates can be attributed to C = C stretching frequency and the lower frequency band at $\sim 1550 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ to the chelated carbonyl group.²¹ However, the perturbed carbonyl band in the substituted chelates shifted to lower frequencies and can be located at $\sim 1530 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Holtzclaw and Collman²² observed such a shift of the perturbed carbonyl for each of the copper chelates in which the carbon between two carbonyl groups is substituted. This may be in part a mass effect. There are no absorption bands at $\sim 1200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the bromo-, chloro- and nitro-substituted beryllium(II) chelates. The unsubstituted beryllium chelates show medium to weak intensity bands at about 1200 cm^{-1} ascribed to a C–H in plane bending vibration.^{3,21,23} The disappearance of the C–H in plane bending vibration at $\sim 1180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ – 1200 cm^{-1} provides evidence for the ring substitution.²

The nitro substituted beryllium chelates showed in addition, a strong band due to the asymmetric C–NO₂ stretching vibration^{5,19} at 1525–1535 cm^{-1} and a symmetric C–NO₂ stretching vibration at 1330 cm^{-1} which are absent in the parent chelates. The spectra of the beryllium chelates and their substituted derivatives showed strong bands near 1040 cm^{-1} and also at $\sim 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are characteristic of Be–O compounds. The absorption at $\sim 1040 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may arise due to the Be–O stretching coupled with the ring deformation vibrations²¹ and the band at $\sim 840 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may arise due to a coupled vibration between the Be–O stretching and C–CH₃ bending modes.

The n.m.r. spectra of the beryllium chelates of 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione, 2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilide, *o*-chloroacetoacetanilide, ω -bromoacetoacetanilide, acetoacetdiethylamide and acetoacetanilide as well as their substituted chelates were recorded mostly in deuterated solvents (Table 1). The spectra of the beryllium chelates Nos. 1, 5, 8 and 10 show signals due to the ring hydrogen at 2.94, 3.64, 4.89 τ and at 4.92 τ respectively and also for methyl, phenyl or methoxy protons. The absence of the signal due to the ring hydrogen in the spectra of these bromo-, chloro- and nitro- substituted chelates confirms substitution of the ring hydrogen. In the n.m.r. spectra of partially substituted chelates (with Nos. 14, 16, 20, 17 and 18) signals of low intensity for the ring hydrogen were observed at 4.54, 4.70, 5.04, 3.89 τ and at 3.65 τ respectively in addition to the signals due to methoxy, methylene, phenyl or *N*-methyl and

N-ethyl protons. The extent of substitution of bromination or chlorination was ascertained from the integrated intensities of the observed two methyl or methylene (corresponding to the substituted and unsubstituted) protons. For instance, under the experimental conditions, about 50% and 30% chlorination of bis-(*o*-chloro-acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) and bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) and 60% and 50% bromination of bis-(ω -bromoacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) and bis-(aceto-acetanilidato)-beryllium(II) respectively could be achieved.

The lower value observed for the methyl protons in the nitro substituted chelates is predominantly due to the continued effect of the electronegativity and anisotropy of the nitro group.²⁴ In the bromo and chloro-substituted chelates also, a similar small shift for the methyl protons was observed. In the spectra of the metal complexes of 2,4-pentanedione with a substituent present at the central carbon atom, Murakami *et al.*²⁵ observed, a downfield shift for methyl protons. Furthermore, Junge *et al.*²⁶ also reported a similar shift in the complexes of 2,4-pentanedione. The observed downfield shift for the methyl protons may be caused by the reduction of electron density at the methyl groups, magnetic anisotropy caused by π -electron current in the chelate ring and by an additional magnetic anisotropy due to the benzene ring which is the result of coordination.

The mass spectra of (1) 2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilide, (2) acetoacetanilide and the beryllium chelates of (1), (2), (3), *o*-chloroacetoacetanilide, (4) 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and (5) acetoacet diethylamide along with the bromo substituted chelates of bis-(1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium (II) and of (1), (3) and (4) have been recorded. The mass spectra of 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and its beryllium chelate and of 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione were reported.^{27,28}

The spectra of all the compounds have shown well defined molecular ions and fragments involving the loss of a ligand. The salient feature observed in the spectra of the beryllium chelates was the formation of the monovalent beryllium chelates by the loss of either phenyl and methyl radicals (in the complexes of 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione) or by the loss of a ligand radical (in acetoacetanilidato complexes). Another phenomenon observed was the loss of a ligand radical from the molecular ion with one oxygen being retained by the beryllium atom. The loss of the fragment $\text{CH}_3\text{-C-CH}=\text{C}=\text{O}$ from the chelates was explained by a skeletal rearrangement process.

The base peak in the spectrum of bis-(1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium(II) observed was the molecular ion m/e 455. The first reaction, upon electron impact, involving the loss of a hydrogen was shown by the ion m/e 454. The reaction appears to resemble the formation of M-1 ions by the loss of aromatic hydrogen from the molecular ions of β -diketonates²⁸ and thio-derivatives.²⁹ The next decomposition involved the loss of .CHO directly,² forming the ion m/e 426. An important mode of decomposition was the loss of a phenyl radical (m/e 378) from the molecular ion leaving a monovalent beryllium chelate as given in Scheme I. It has been demonstrated recently that the valencies of the metal atoms can alter during ion reactions and that the valency changes may be an important factor contributing to the driving force of such reactions.^{11,13}

TABLE 1

N.M.R. spectral data of bis-(β-diketonato)-beryllium(II) chelates and their derivatives

Sr.No.	Compound	Ring H	Methyl	Methoxy	Methylene	Phenyl
1.	Bis-(1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanediono)-beryllium(II)	2.94 ⁺ (0.4)*	—	—	—	2.57, 2.52, 2.49 (2.4); 1.95, 1.89, 1.82, 1.79 (1.6)
2.	Bis(2-bromo-1,3-diphenyl-propanediono)-beryllium(II)	—	—	—	—	2.59, 2.54 (3.6); 2.29, 2.24, 2.17, 2.14 (2.4)
3.	Bis-(2-chloro-1,3-diphenyl-propanediono)-beryllium(II)	—	—	—	—	2.6, 2.54, 2.5 (2.3); 1.99, 1.92, 1.87, 1.82 (1.6)
4.	Bis-(2-nitro-1,3-diphenyl-propanediono)-beryllium(II)	—	—	—	—	2.5 (3.6); 2.02, 1.95, 1.89 (2.4)
5.	Bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II)	3.64 (0.5)	7.75 (1.5)	—	—	2.07, 1.99, 1.94, 1.9 (1.0); 2.59, 2.54, 2.50 (1.5)
6.	Bis-(2-bromo-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II)	—	7.49 (2.6)	—	—	2.60, 2.57 (2.6); 2.39, 2.34, 2.25, 2.22 (1.70)
7.	Bis-(2-nitro-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II)	—	7.52 (1.9)	—	—	2.5, 2.44 (3.1)
8.	Bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloro-acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.89 (0.5)	7.97 (1.5)	6.22 6.17(3.0)	—	3.12, 2.1 (0.5)
9.	Bis-(3-bromo-2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	—	7.67 (1.7)	6.29 6.15(3.4)	—	3.09, 2.12 (0.5)
10.	Bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.92 (1.0)	8.00 (3.0)	—	—	2.94, 2.82 (4.0) 2.09, 1.95 (1.0);
11.	Bis-(3-bromo-o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	—	7.65 (2.0)	—	—	2.92, 2.87, 2.67 (2.0); 1.97, 1.87, 1.84 (1.2)
12.	Bis-(3-nitro-o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	—	7.34 (2.8)	—	—	2.87, 2.82, 2.64 (3.6); 2.17, 2.05, 2.02 (0.9)
13.	Bis-(ω-bromo acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.45 (0.3)	—	—	6.09 (0.6)	2.85, 2.70, 2.50 (1.5)
14.	Bromination product of bis-(ω-bromoacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.54 (0.1)	—	—	6.14(0.2) 5.8(0.3)	2.82, 2.57, 2.44 (0.5)
15.	Bis-(acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.75	8.13	—	—	—
16.	Bromination product of bis-(acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	4.70	6.20 (0.4) 5.95(0.2)	—	—	2.82, 2.69, 2.55 (2.3)
17.	Chlorination product of bis-(o-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II)	3.89 (0.6)	7.97(1.8) 7.70(0.9)	—	—	—
18.	Chlorination product of bis-(1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II)	3.65 (0.6)	2.65(0.7) 2.23(2.0)	—	—	2.64, 2.55 (2.0); 2.1, 2.04, 1.99, 1.94 (0.7)
19.	Bis(acetoacetyl-diethylamidato)-beryllium(II)	5.19	8.10	8.20 (N-methyl)	6.62 (N-ethyl)	—
20.	Bromination product of bis-(acetoacetyl-diethylamidato)-beryllium(II)	5.04	8.05	8.97 8.85 8.62 8.72	(N-ethyl) (N-ethyl) (N-ethyl) (N-ethyl)	—

The spectra of the compounds Nos. 1-12, 16, 17, 18 and 20 were recorded in CDCl₃, compound Nos. 13 and 14 in CD₃COCD₂, compound No. 19 in CCl₄ and compound No. 15 in pyridine.

* The values in parentheses are the integrated intensities.

† Values, τ.

The expulsion of a phenyl radical was supported by the meta-stable peak at m/e 314. (calcd. 314.1). This was followed by a decarbonylation (giving an ion m/e 350) and a further loss of carbon monoxide forming m/e 322 ion. An interesting feature was the loss of a ligand radical giving the ion m/e 248 with oxygen remaining intact with the beryllium atom as illustrated in Scheme II.

The direct loss of a ligand radical from the molecular ion was shown by the ion m/e 232 which was confirmed by the meta-stable peak at 142.3 (calcd. 142).

The mass spectrum of bis-(2-bromo-1,3-diphenylpropanediono)-beryllium(II) showed a strong molecular ion m/e 611, with isotopic patterns corresponding to the presence of two bromine atoms. The ratio for the isotopic cluster of bromine atoms $P : P+2 : P+4$, observed was 1 : 1.9 : 1 (calcd. 1.02 : 1.99 : 0.97). The first important fragment ion was seen at m/e 534 corresponding to the loss of a phenyl radical from the molecular ion leaving a monovalent beryllium chelate similar to that in Scheme I. The meta-stable peak at m/e 466 (calcd. 466.2) supported this expulsion. This was followed by the loss of a bromine atom giving the ion m/e 455.

The spectrum of bis-(1-phenyl,1,3-butanediono)-beryllium(II) showed the ion m/e 330 due to the loss of a hydrogen atom. The next mode of decomposition was the loss of a methyl radical (m/e 316) from the molecular ion leaving a monovalent beryllium chelate. The direct loss of .CHO from the molecular ion gave the ion m/e 302. The loss of a ketone radical from the molecular ion was shown by the ion m/e 289, which was confirmed by the meta-stable peak at 252.4. The next mode of decomposition was the loss of a phenyl radical (m/e 254) followed by the loss of carbon monoxide to give a weak peak at m/e 226. The molecular ion lost a ligand radical with its one oxygen atom retained by the beryllium atom to give the fragment m/e 186 similar to that in Scheme II.

The mass spectrum of bis-(2-bromo-1-phenyl-1,3-butanediono)-beryllium (II) showed molecular ion m/e 487 with isotopic pattern corresponding to the presence of two bromine atoms (observed ratio 1.06 : 2 : 1). The decomposition pattern was similar to the bromo chelate.

The mass spectrum of bis-(acetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) showed the molecular ion m/e 361. The ion m/e 360 was formed by the loss of a hydrogen atom. The loss of a phenylamine residue, C_6H_5NH , from the molecular ion gave rise to the ion m/e 269. The loss of a methyl radical from the molecular ion (m/e 346) leaves the monovalent beryllium chelate similar to that in Scheme I. The direct loss of a ligand radical was observed at m/e 185 leaving the monovalent beryllium chelate (Scheme III).

The loss of the fragment $CH_3-C-CH=C=O$ could be explained through a rearrangement process (Scheme IV) by which the molecule cleaved off $CH_3-C-CH=C=O$ at m/e 277.

This expulsion of $(C_4H_4O_2)$ was supported by the meta-stable peak at 212.4 (calcd. 212.5).

The mass spectrum of bis-(*o*-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) showed an intense molecular ion m/e 429, with an isotopic cluster corresponding to the two chlorine atoms.

The loss of the fragment from the molecular ion gave rise to the ion m/e 303 leaving the fragment as shown in Scheme V.

Another feature was the loss of a chlorine atom (m/e 394) from the molecular ion. The meta-stable peak at 361.2 supported this assumption. The loss of a ligand radical from the molecular ion giving m/e 219, resulted in the formation of a monovalent beryllium chelate similar to that shown in Scheme III. The expulsion of the fragment $CH_3-C-CH=C=O$ according to Scheme IV from the molecular ion at m/e 345 was also observed.

The spectrum of bis-(3-bromo-*o*-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) showed strong molecular ion m/e 585 with isotopic cluster corresponding to two bromine and two chlorine atoms. The ratio observed for the isotopic cluster pattern of chlorine and bromine,

$P : P+2 : P+4 : P+6$ was $1.1 : 3.0 : 2.7 : 1$ (calcd. $1.1 : 3.1 : 2.8 : 1$). A skeletal rearrangement process similar to that in Scheme IV was also observed to take place giving off $\text{CH}_3\text{-C-CBr} = \text{C} = \text{O}$ at m/e 423. This was followed by the loss of hydrogen bromide

$\begin{array}{c} \parallel \\ \text{O} \end{array}$ forming the ion m/e 343. The loss of the fragment from the molecular ion was observed (m/e 459) leaving a skeleton similar to that shown in Scheme V. This view was supported by the presence of a meta-stable peak at 360.2 (calcd. 360).

The mass spectrum of bis-(2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) showed a strong molecular ion at m/e 549 with an isotopic cluster corresponding to two chlorine atoms. The ion at m/e 465 was formed through a rearrangement process similar to that shown in Scheme IV and the meta-stable peak at m/e 394.2 supported the expulsion of $\text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_2$. This was accompanied by the loss of a methyl radical to give m/e 450. The other modes of decomposition from the molecular ion were the direct loss of CHO (m/e 520)

and the loss of a methoxy radical (m/e 518). The loss of the fragment at

m/e 363 resulted in a skeleton similar to that shown in Scheme V. The direct loss of the ligand radical from the molecular ion, according to Scheme III observed at m/e 279, however, resulted in the formation of a monovalent beryllium chelate.

The spectrum of bis-(3-bromo-2,5-dimethoxy-4-chloroacetoacetanilidato)-beryllium(II) showed the molecular ion m/e 705 with isotopic pattern corresponding to the presence of two chlorine and two bromine atoms. The peak at m/e 543 could be due to the skeletal rearrangement process (Scheme IV) observed in all the acetoacetanilidato compounds. The other features observed were similar to those of the parent chelate.

The spectrum of bis-(acetoacetdiethylamidato)-beryllium(II) showed fairly intense molecular ion m/e 321. The loss of a hydrogen atom was observed at m/e 320. The loss of a methyl radical from the molecular ion resulted in the formation of a monovalent beryllium chelate (Scheme III). The ions m/e 292 and m/e 278 respectively, were due to the loss of ethyl and acetyl radicals. The ion m/e 249 could be formed by the loss of the fragment

$\begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \\ \text{N} \\ \diagdown \text{C}_2\text{H}_5 \end{array}$. The meta-stable peak at 212.5 supported this expulsion. The direct loss of the ligand radical from the molecular ion however resulted in the formation of a monovalent beryllium chelate similar to that shown in Scheme III. The fragment $\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3\text{-C-CH} = \text{C-N} \\ \parallel \qquad \qquad \qquad | \\ \text{O} \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{O} \end{array}$

$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2$ was observed at m/e 156.

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